

Artificial intelligence and its prospective use in armed forces

¹Javed Ahmad

Assistance Professor, Indus University

Email: samojaved@live.com

Shamaila Amir

Fellow of PhD in Linguistics, HIESS, Hamdard University, Karachi, Pakistan

Email: shaminhasan@hotmail.com

Fayyaz Ahmad

Fellow of MS (Behavioural Sciences), NUST, Islamabad, Pakistan

Email: fayaz7522@gmail.com

Abstract: Since the innovation of computers, their performance at various tasks went on increasing exponentially. Computer systems are developed to solve diversified problems, the process at very high speed, reduce time, and bring easiness in every field of life. To peak a little deeper inside the computer science technology, an era named Artificial Intelligence (AI) develops systems or machines as Intelligent as human brains. AI aims to look up device activities in dealing with difficult tasks. Smart machines have now become a reality and researchers are designing such systems that can copy human thought, understand speech, defeat the best human chess player, and achieve many other advantages. Armed forces of every country play a vital role in nation-building by providing community services and facilities to remote areas apart from their operational capabilities to perform their core jobs. Few AI applications that may be applied for operational capabilities and for the sake of nation-building by Armed Forces are analyzed in this paper. On the basis of the analysis of prospective use of AI for Armed Forces, conclusions are drawn and recommendations are made by the researchers.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, armed forces, use of AI for armed forces, etc.

Introduction:

Since the innovation of computers, their performance at various tasks went on increasing exponentially. Computer systems are developed to solve diversified problems, the process at very high speed, reduce time, and bring easiness in every field of life. To peak a little deeper inside the computer science technology, an era named Artificial Intelligence (AI) develops systems or machines as Intelligent as human brains (Zilis, 2016). John McCarthy, the father of AI defines this field as “The science and engineering of Making Intelligent machines, especially intelligent Computer Programs”. In other words, Artificial Intelligence is a means of “engineering system, an automated computer-controlled robot or computer software that behaves intelligently as a human being.” The goal of developing of AI system is only possible to achieve only by studying and understanding the human brain and its structure, its working phenomena, how human brain thinks, learns and makes a decision in different circumstances and problem-solving aptitude. Artificial Intelligence has enormous significance in modern technologies and has greater scope almost in every aspect of life. AI’s emphasis is on creating machines that behave like human beings and

¹ Corresponding author

perform critical analysis over complex problems to make more comprehensive decision-making. Today systems have become so smart and have the potential to mimic human intelligence, recognize speech in different natural languages, understand the health condition of the patients, generate reports and diagnose accordingly, suggest the best possible route to a vehicle, identify objects with virtual reality beat human in Chess and Go games players, Vast range of other applications which were not possible with traditional data processing mechanism, are possible now because of AI. AI aims to look up device activities in dealing with difficult tasks. Smart machines have now become a reality and researchers are designing such systems which can copy human thought, understand speech, defeat the best human chess player, and achieve many other advantages (Bellman, 1978).

AI and its goals:

AI is identified with the following goals:

- i. **Human Intelligence in Machines.** Designing machines that recognize patterns, sense, and act like human beings.
- ii. **Designing Expert Systems.** Systems that show sign of intelligent behavior, gain knowledge, exhibit, enlighten and suggest the users according to given input.

Artificial intelligence technologies:

The marketplace for artificial intelligence advancements is thriving. Artificial Intelligence is entailing a range of technologies and tools. Few of these recent technologies are as given below:

Fig 1: Speech Recognition (Zhang, 2017).

- i. **Natural Language Processing and Speech Recognition:** It is a technology that recognizes the human voice and performs specific commands given by the

individual. The system understands human natural language and converts it into a computer-readable form to process a specific task. It is widely used in mobile application and interactive voice responsive robot agents (Abadi et al, 2016). Google Assistant and Siri are the best examples of such type systems.

Fig 2: Natural Language Processing (Harne, 2016)

- ii. **Virtual Agent (VA):** A smart character that behaves like an online agent for providing customer services. Virtual Agent communicates with users and responds according to queries and performs human-like behavior. One of the good examples of Virtual Agent is Louise developed by a French developer (Newman, 2017).
- iii. **Machine learning (ML):** Machine learning is one of the key advancements of AI. Developing intelligent machines having the potential to learn from existing executions and change their behavior accordingly. Actually, ML is a technique widely used in most enterprise applications for the purpose of classification or prediction over data sets provided. ML is providing algorithms, frameworks, development toolkits, and different models (data & development).
- iv. **Deep Learning/ Neural Network (DL/NN):** The latest development in AI is deep learning platforms or neural networks. Computer systems took decades to think deeply like the human brain. The system designed with this technology changes the behavior (from trained data sets and executions) according to conditions and circumstances. Modern Computer defeated humans in GO game soon after the invention of the deep learning system. Deep learning system have an artificial neural networks like the human brain and multiple abstraction layers which store behavior/ pattern of machine.

Fig 3: Virtual Agent ChatBot (Reed, 2016)

- v. **Biometric:** It is another useful technology of AI which recognize humans physically or with behavioral patterns. Biometric Systems are widely used in Surveillance systems to identify access control and keep record of individuals with the help of Thumb Impression, eye Retina, heartbeat, voice recognition, face detection or combination.

Fig 4: Biometric System (Wilson, n.d.)

- vi. **Robotics:** An area of AI which develops a system that not only thinks or is intelligent like human but performs another task of a human being like bring a tray of cups. Robots have efficient processors, various sensors, and massive memory to exhibit smartness. An intelligent robot can perform almost all tasks a human being can perform. Robots are very helpful for human beings. Robots have significant applications ranging from home servants to work in an extremely complex environment where a human being can not as in industries where the temperature is more than 100 centigrade, nearby volcanos, in heavy rain, deep inside sea, space exploration, and many more (Morris, 2015). Nowadays, advanced countries are investing more enough on this technology to create intelligent robot cops which can work as a traffic controller as well as a fighting cop.

Fig 5: Robotics (Romeo, 2018)

- vii. **Gaming:** AI supports gaming also. Modern games are AI-based; machine learning and deep learning techniques are embedded in games to strengthen the strategy of the game. In gaming computer finds the patterns of users and response on those patterns. The first computer program IBM's Deep Blue became the best world champion in a chess match, Garry Kasparov, in an exhibition game.
- viii. **Expert Systems:** One of the key pillars of AI is Expert systems. Expert systems are the integrated machine, software and an information system to impart analysis and advising. The system suggests clarification and recommendations to the users.

Artificial Intelligence is the key technology in many of today's applications in all fields including the military. The technology is being used to support decision making at various levels of defense operations such as measures of forces readiness, consistency, and potential, complex mission planning, and assimilation of data from various sources. Moreover, AI research also

addresses the opportunities presented such as decision making in agile conditions. The use of this technology opens up continuous possibilities in the armed forces.

Fig 6: Gaming (Renstrom, 2017)

The military architectures of the modern world consist of land and space-based sensors, a new range of sea, unmanned combat aerial vehicles (UCAV), and missile defense technologies. Near future defense, organizations would have intelligent, fast, and small ammunitions to cause complex circumstances for opponents. AI has gained advances in the operational and tactical situations and can decide appropriate action. Furthermore, an AI system would facilitate to collect data from different sources simultaneously, clean data accordingly to get required data to analyze as per need, and give recommendations to the concerned authority for making more appropriate decisions or prepare countermeasures for future (Boeriu, 2016; Faggella, 2016; Xiao, 2016; Blanchard, 2016).

Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Armed Forces for Nation Building:

Armed forces of every country play a vital role in nation-building by providing community services and facilities to remote areas. Few of these AI applications which may be applied for the sake of nation-building by Armed Forces may be categorized as under:

- i. **Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare:** AI has great significance in healthcare and medication. Computer vision and machine learning techniques simplify the diagnosis of breast cancer, brain cancer, lung cancer, brain tumor, and many other diseases from MRI, X-Ray, or ultrasound images. On the other end, the Patient Record Management System can keep records of patients' (Disease, Prescription, consultancy, and medical reports, blood pressure, heart rate, etc.) automatically from devices attached to him/her or manually by nursing staff (Essays, 2018; Yudkowsky, 2008).

To extend Expert Systems that suggest prescription to patients after finding health history or asking symptoms from patients. Providing health care is one of

the main concerns of the Armed Forces. To a great extent, IBM's Watson is considered one of the best technologies in the world because it is capable to understand natural language and can also respond to asked questions. This system mines data of patients and other data sources that are available and then form a hypothesis. This hypothesis is then presented with a schema having confidence scoring. The doctor and the patients in military hospitals can be assisted by AI because it can imitate and match human intelligence into computer technology in the following ways

1. It can provide a laboratory for the examination in military hospitals.
2. It can represent and catalog medical information about patients and diseases.
3. It can devise novel tools and provide support in decision making and medical research and diagnosis.
4. It can integrate various activities in the medical sciences.
5. It can also integrate activities in software and cognitive sciences.
6. AI can also offer a discipline that is rich in content for scientific medical communities of future.

Fig 7: Artificial intelligence in health care (Trapollo, 2018)

- ii. **Artificial Intelligence in customer services:** The military can apply Robotic process automation especially in tasks that are repetitive in nature and normally performed by humans. A machine learning algorithm is another tool that can be integrated into analytics and platforms with the Customer Relationship Model to get help in retrieving the information. This will make to serve customers in a much better way in local military businesses. Apart from that Chatbots are incorporated

into websites and can provide immediate service to customers of military services. The help of academics and IT consultancies can be sought for automation of civilian job positions in the military also (Yudkowsky, 2008).

- iii. **Artificial Intelligence in Education:** A large network of educational institutes of armed forces is often set to provide quality education to children and wards of armed forces as well as civilians. For that matter, AI can be used to automate grading, giving educators more time. Automated Chatbots, examination systems, smart simulators, and an expert system like encyclopedias bring easiness to education with the help of AI. In the education sector, the military can also educate, evaluate/ assess students' performance using machine learning techniques and smart simulators and deploy a biometric attendance system for employees or students (Yudkowsky, 2008; Yudelson et al., 2013).

Fig 8: Robot performing as a teacher (Lakhani, 2019)

- iv. **Artificial Intelligence in Autonomous vehicles:** There are self-driving cars which like human beings need sensors and brains installed in those so that these can understand the world around and collect and process actions based on information they gather through their sensors and brains. These autonomous vehicles are equipped with advanced tools that gather information such as long-range radar, various cameras. These latest tools of various technologies can also be used in military and general transport used in armed forces in different capacities to collect different pieces of information for different purposes. It is necessary that this gathered information is process and analysis is made based on it. in this case, AI can become very useful when compared to the human brain and analysis. It has different applications for vehicles used by armed forces and the most immediate and useful ones to be introduced in armed forces may be as follows (Yudkowsky, 2008; Xiao, 2016; Boeriu, 2016; Faggella, 2016):

1. AI can direct the car to fueling stations in case of running low on fuel.
2. It can adjust the trips directions analyzing the traffic conditions by finding the quickest route for transportation.
3. It can incorporate and establish advanced communication, such as speech recognition, with passengers and personnel onboard.
4. AI can establish natural language interfaces and provide virtual assistance technologies to various services provided by Armed forces.

Fig 9: An autonomous vehicle (Schroer, 2019)

- v. **Artificial Intelligence in Robotics:** If introduced in the military, it will help the armed forces to address various challenges which they face in taking care of the dependent aging population. It will in fact allow much longer independence by drastically reducing and even bringing down accidents and accidental deaths. It will further enable armed forces in their disaster response in case of floods, earthquakes, and other natural calamities and dangerous situations specific to military establishments such as nuclear meltdown at power plants. AI robots in military industries may be used for other purposes like handling of material and other activities such as cutting, weld, coat, drill, and polish various materials, etc. In the field of medicine, AI Robots can prove very helpful in clinical tests because they can carry out hundreds of clinical tests in very little time. Moreover, during the training of armed personnel AI robots can be used in various land and space assignments such as for musketry, climbing rocks, exploring the space, to quote some. Furthermore, AI robot can be used for the sake of information and public

relations offices such as for movie making same as Disney's engineers have created hundreds of AI robots.

- vi. **Artificial Intelligence in Cyborg Technology:** Human body parts are the main limitations of being human. Shimon Whiteson, a famous researcher, considers that in the future, humans will be able to augment with computers and enhance several abilities that are naturally inbuilt. Many of such cyborg enhancements would be useful for convenience while some others would serve for practical purposes. On the other hand, AI can become useful for people who have amputated limbs, hearts, or other body parts, etc. Because brains will be able to communicate with a robotic limb and give a person or patient more control. There are lots of limitations which the amputees deal with in their daily life which can be significantly reduced with the help of cyborg technology (Xiong et al., 2016; Bellman, 1978).

Fig 10: AI in Cyborg technology (Espirit Technologies Private Limited, 2018)

Operational Application of Artificial Intelligence in Armed Forces:

Defense forces across the globe are embedding AI into weapons. Different countries are also using AI in other systems that are used by forces on land, water, and space platforms. Efficient warfare systems that are very less reliant on human beings are successfully being developed and used by militaries. In armed forces, AI applications can also lead to increase synergy and enhanced performance of warfare systems at the same time involving less maintenance. It can also be used to empower weapons which are autonomous and high-speed in carrying out collaborative attacks. As far as warfare platforms are concerned, the following are identified as prospective uses of AI in armed forces:

- i. **Cybersecurity:** A military system like any other is very much vulnerable to cyber-attacks or even more. It can result in the loss of highly classified military information and damage to military networks or systems. Following points are to be considered in this regard:
 1. Military information is always at threat and the enemy can use different cyber thread models. AI can help armed forces in this regard because the intelligent systems which are equipped with AI will automatically protect or resist intruders or hackers against military networks, devices and computers, programs, and classified data from all sorts of access which are deemed unauthorized. In addition, the military security system which is AI-enabled, can record cyber-attack patterns and ultimately help to develop different counter-attacks tools so that these attacks can be tackled effectively and efficiently (Bellman, 1978; AI Business, 2016).
 2. Cybersecurity solution with AI is highly in demand because cybersecurity faces a high level of risks which are resulted through the data breaches in military networking systems. Armed forces may require security products with the capability to identify threats and predict what is going to happen before some threat they can actually damage or breach military and defense networks. Analysis of dangers of leaked intelligence of cybersecurity seems to remain a high priority for its armed forces while hackers can be utilized by enemy forces for breach of secrets or sabotage existing systems. Cybersecurity threats to the military obviously come in numerous categories. In this situation, AI is capable to play a major role to take preventative measures. The software can also identify and analyze different digital situations, e.g. an e-mail or USB drive that may trap or tool for implanting malware, and then neutralize any cyber threat that is dormant and waiting for some military operator before becoming active to breach or damage military network through malware (Essays, 2018; AI Business, 2016).
 3. Software tools are very successful in identifying and predicting cyber threats to military networks when they use artificial intelligence (US Marine Corps, 2016). An example of this is London-based “BAE Systems” which is a defense, security, and aerospace DARPA entered into a collaboration worth \$ 5.2 with BAE Systems and developed CHASE software that is capable of identifying and predicting cyber threats. If used in armed forces, software like CHASE might initially require datasets that can be labeled and can indicate the “normal” values for different metrics from the military’s internal network systems or servers and work on intrusion detections which are based on non-AI systems. This will make such software capable of the identification of baseline reading for standard operating network conditions of armed forces. Due to older security intrusions, this software would be trained to identify different anomalies experienced in the military network characteristics (Blasko, 2011; Essays, 2018). Once the software “learns” what are the parameter values that could come from an active threat to cybersecurity, it can also be used to prompt personnel deployed as security

- analysts with the help of the dashboard. This procedure would ensure that each new security threat is identified quickly and correctly (AI Business, 2016).
4. CHASE or any other software that is capable of using AI for cybersecurity, can monitor normal levels of download data that occurred by a department per day. It can then indicate potential threats to security if that department exceeds allowed or normal per day download prediction. For identifying and analyzing unknown files and detecting cyber threats e.g. a malware much before it can breach a military network, software like CHASE are highly authenticated. Likewise, remote devices such as laptops, tablets, cell phones, or sensors which are called “endpoints.” are very vulnerable to cyber-attacks. This type of software automatically monitors these remote devices including weapons systems, mobile devices, and aircraft. It is claimed by Spark Cognition that Deep Armor has been successfully used to catch and block many cybersecurity threats, such as the famous WannaCry ransomware attack, Popcorn Time, and Adylkuzz (Blasko, 2011; AI Business, 2016).
 5. Similarly, Cylance that is a startup company funded by Q-Tel, works on a system of predictive analytics. Safelite’s VP of IT commented on Cylance’s capabilities states, “Cylance detected and stopped tens of thousands of events per day. Not one of them was noticed or acted upon by the existing anti-virus system.” On the other hand in a case study, Matthew Coy stated that low administration efforts are required to manage Cylance PROTECT which has resulted in notable reductions in expenses by Safelite. According to his estimate, the time which was required in managing their old anti-virus product was approximately 150 hours per week (AI Business, 2016).
- ii. **Target Recognition:** The speed and accuracy of AI-based equipment are highly focused on defense forces. Target recognition with the accuracy of almost 100% in complex warfare conditions enrich forces against opponents. Along with accuracy and speed, smart weapons are very intelligent to recognize the behavior of target and work in different conditions and circumstances and then activate as when required. The power of computer vision and machine learning techniques enable AI weapons to recognize objects with accuracy whereas the neural network technique brings smartness to the device to understand the behavior of the target and activate accordingly. So a country which is fighting a war against several terrorist organizations, anti-state organizations, and neighboring country threats, should have AI embedded advanced technology weapons to strengthen armed forces to be more accurate on targets. An example of an AI-enabled system DARPA’s which recognizes target with the help of Synthetic-Aperture Radar (SAR) images (Sputnik, 2016; Keller, 2015; Holmes, 2016; AI Business, 2016).
 - iii. **Threat Monitoring & Situational Awareness:** Monitoring of threats to the military system and situational awareness both rely very heavily on the military’s Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance operations (Blasko, 2011). These

ISR operations may also be used to collect and process useful information that can support military activities of a wide range. If ISR missions are carried out through unmanned systems, these can be remotely operated and also sent on a route that is predefined. By equipping ISR systems with AI in armed forces, assistance may be provided to personnel who are deployed on threat monitoring. Likewise, situational awareness of deployed personnel may also be enhanced through AI. Unmanned aerial vehicles or drones, (Boeriu, 2016; Faggella, 2016) when integrated AI, can effectively patrol areas adjacent to borders and identify any sort of potential threats. Moreover, these drones can also transmit information to a quick response force or to respond to teams about these potential threats well in advance. Using drones in the military can strengthen the security of borders and military bases (US Marine Corps, 2016). It can definitely increase military personnel safety and efficacy on the battlefield or at remote areas also (Sputnik, 2016; Keller, 2015; Holmes, 2016; AI Business, 2016; Xiao, 2016).

- iv. **Autonomous Weapons and Weapons Targeting:** Accuracy to hit a target and the extent a target system is quick to lock on to its target are two important things on which the working of a target system is judged. Countermeasures for these styles of targeting are gaining popularity so it is important that electronic targeting systems must be capable of being less susceptible to these countermeasures applied against targeting systems. It is evident that machine learning and computer vision are going to be the next application for this hide and seek game of technology and targeting. The use of Computer vision for identifying and tracking targets by autonomous weapon platforms is very common today. In this case, the weapon initially becomes autonomous when the AI system becomes able to identify and track its targets in space. The AI behind the targeting in this situation needs to be trained to lock the strategic targets and focus its firepower on the target. It needs after this to alert the operator who is monitoring the platform. This strategic target can be anything like an enemy aircraft which is flying at extreme speeds in contested space or a rocket which is meant to be fired at some populated area or even an armored carrier, with personnel, driving up a minored road. However, Currently, no autonomous weapon platforms are being designed which can fire without the express approval of their monitoring operators. Traditionally manned systems are susceptible to human distraction and needs while autonomous weapon systems are not like that. This is a strategic advantage of autonomous weapons over the conventional weapon system which is manned. Computer vision of an autonomous weapon system is like an ever-vigilant eye that is trained on the skies above and prevents surprise rocket/ missiles attacks and enables them to target and shoot down enemy rockets/missiles in the air even before they could hit a populated area. On the other hand very valuable seconds if not responded are wasted and the results become destructive if the human operator is not attentive while posted on a system (AI Business, 2016; Blanchard, 2016).
- v. **Combat Simulation & Training:** Simulation & training as a multidisciplinary field is paired with system and software engineering and computer science. It constructs computerized models and acquaints soldiers with all combat systems which are deployed during military operations. The military may invest in the simulation & training applications for its armed forces. Navy and Army may each

- conduct warfare analysis, which may lead them to initiate different sensor simulation programs just as US Navy has enlisted various companies like Leidos, and SAIC which supports its programs and other the other hand the US Army gets support for its programs through various firms like CACI, and Torch Technologies or Millennium Engineering (Blasko, 2011; AI Business, 2016)
- vi. **AI & Data Information Processing:** AI can particularly be useful for quick and efficient processing of data in large volumes and ultimately obtain information which is valuable for armed forces. AI can also assist in culling and aggregating information that was gathered from different datasets and can further acquire and sum up information. If armed forces work on these lines, this advanced analytical ability will enable military personnel to recognize patterns of information and derive correlations
- vii. **Autonomous Technologies:** Michael Griffin who is Autonomous Vehicles Defense Undersecretary for Research and Engineering, states that those military operators which perform duties to provide logistic support suffer from a minimum of 50 % of the casualties when they are at war. Griffin said, “If that can be done by an automated unmanned vehicle with a relatively simple AI driving algorithm where I don’t have to worry about pedestrians and road signs and all of that, why wouldn’t I do that?” Moreover, the safety regulations and training related to an autonomous vehicle which are used for military purposes can be at reduced sophistication level when compared to those which are being sold to the public. When human lives are at risk, it is easy to do utilitarian calculations of value through AI as an autonomous vehicles can operate with relatively less concern about the drivers if it is on a mission of saving the lives of vehicle operators (AI Business, 2016; Blasko, 2011; Boeriu, 2016; Faggella, 2016).
- viii. **Logistics & Transportation:** In the military, AI can be crucially beneficial in logistics and transport. It can be used in the transportation of goods, ammunition, and armaments effectively. To move troops that are essentially required for successful military operations AI is compulsory. Keeping these facts in view and analyzing the geographical conditions of a country, AI can be very helpful in the effective transportation of all these items. Integrating AI with military transportation can reduce the costs and human efforts that are presently applied to military operations (Xiong et al., 2016). It can also help military fleets in detecting anomalies and ultimately predict any sort of component failures immediately. For example, the US Army recently in collaboration with IBM and used its Watson AI platform with the purpose to get help in pre-identifying maintenance problems in Stryker combat vehicles (Boeriu, 2016; Faggella, 2016; Xiao, 2016). As a famous saying is, “Knowledge is power” AI is very much capable to enhance knowledge and helps a decision-maker to make better and well-informed decisions. Large edges can be gained in armed forces in logistics and maintenance movements and operations. AI is capable of allowing to provide efficient and data-backed logistics. It can also work for the maintenance of military equipment in a much better way than humans (Blasko, 2011; AI Business, 2016).
- ix. **Battlefield Healthcare:** AI in Army and Airforce specifically can be integrated with “Robotic Surgical Systems” (RSS) and “Robotic Ground Platforms” (RGPs) which can provide surgical support in remote areas of operation and also help in

evacuation activities if required. The US is particularly much advanced in the development of RSS and RGPs apart from a number of other systems like that facilitate specifically for healthcare on the battlefield. These systems which are equipped with AI can mine medical records of soldiers and also provide assistance in complex diagnosis. For instance, the research team of IBM's Watson which partnered with the US Veterans Administration developed a clinical reasoning prototype which is known as EMRA i.e. Electronic Medical Record Analyzer. This is a preliminary technology that has been specifically designed to use techniques of machine learning to process electronic medical records of patients. This system automatically identifies and ranks the most critical problem of health suffered by the patients and soldiers (AI Business, 2016).

Conclusion:

On the basis of analysis of prospective use of AI for Armed Forces, following are concluded:

- i. AI is successfully being used worldwide in militaries of advanced and developing countries.
- ii. The use of AI in armed forces for operations other than combat is very successful in education, logistics, healthcare is highly recommended for analysts all over the world due to the low cost of maintenance and less workforce.
- iii. The use of AI for combat and related operations requires an advanced level of technology with a considerable amount of expenses.
- iv. AI can be used in all three forces i.e. army, navy, and air force.
- v. There are numerous military and non-military fields where AI has its prospective uses.
- vi. Any country which is important from a geostrategic point of view, or in the wake of the war against terrorism or/and having potential threats from its neighboring countries requires advanced AI technology strengthen its armed forces to be accurate in security and targets.

Recommendations:

On the basis of conclusion, following are recommended for the perspective use of AI in armed forces:

- i. Initially, AI may be introduced for non-combat operations of armed forces in a few of their installations such as hospitals on an experimental basis.
- ii. Combat use of AI may be introduced for Army which operates in remote areas and borders for protection and accuracy of the target.
- iii. Later, after successful results of experimental use in the Army, Navy and Air Force may develop AI applications for operational uses.
- iv. The world is afraid of the future of AI as machines have got to understand like human beings started to perform actions on their own. These aspects of the machine

might create lots of difficulties and problems for military environments. This needs to be addressed prior to using AI in Armed Forces.

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